

THE HISTORY OF MINIATURE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract. *In this article, the history of miniature art and its importance in human life is discussed in the article about the history of the creation of miniature art in the territory of our Republic and its role in human life.*

Keywords: *miniature, art, image, tool, middle ages, literature, garb, fine art, writing, interior design, painting, miniature.*

Medieval art began in different countries at different times. In particular, when we study the art of eastern countries, we can witness that the medieval art in China, Japan, and Korea started a little earlier than in other countries and continued in the 19th century. The art of the Middle Ages is the main stage in the development of the national culture of the peoples of the world. From this period, the national specific arts of the peoples were formed, and many art schools began to appear. The beauty of life was depicted in the art of the Middle Ages, and the grace of nature was reflected through human feelings.

It is known that a renaissance in the field of fine arts took place in the Eastern countries of the Middle Ages. In particular, the wonderful painting type of visual arts has developed widely in connection with book graphics. As a result, Arab (Baghdad), Iranian (Tabriz), Isfahan, Shiraz, Turkish, Movarounnahr, Indian, Azerbaijan, Herat, Bukhara, Samarkand miraculous painting schools appeared. A number of artists such as Mirak Naqqosh, Kamoliddin Behzod, Kasim Ali Ustaz Gung, Abdullah ibn Fazil, Ota Mirok, Kesu, Ustad Shamsiddin, Abdul Baqi Tabrizi were at the head of these schools.

People's dreams about humanity were reflected in the works of visual art created during this period. It was important for the artist not only to depict reality, but also to express an idea through the image he worked on. When we study the works of Eastern painters and pedagogues of the Middle Ages, miniatures and memorabilia occupy the main place in these periods.

Miniature (French: miniature; Latin: minium - red paint) is a wonderful visual art work with very elegant artistic methods. The term miniature is used for elegant small-scale paintings created to decorate medieval manuscripts, as well as small-scale paintings made on bone, parchment, metal, porcelain, and sometimes household items, and is considered a lacquered miniature. In addition, there is also the field of artistic miniatures, and the fields of artistic miniatures such as book and portrait miniatures are widespread. In book miniatures, the pictures are made in color with tempera, gouache, glue, watercolor and other paints, directly on the pages of manuscript books, and the patterns on them are combined with the decorations of these books.

The miniature has been known since ancient times. Paintings on ancient Egyptian papyri were painted with pale colors on a flat surface. In the Middle Ages, the characteristics of folk art entered the miniature. In the Gothic miniatures of the 13th and 15th centuries, the desire to represent nature increased, the pictures were explained with text, the forms were revived, the landscape, interior, and architectural borders were given a lot of space. Among the great masters of miniatures in France, A.Boneyo, Jacquemar Eden and others created effectively.

Miniature manuscripts were widespread in the East in the 12th-19th centuries as illustrations of manuscript books and specially made paintings. First, scientific manuscripts (for example, the Arabic translation of Dioscorides' treatise "Medicines" on medicine, Abu Rayhan Beruni's "Osar Ulboqiya" - "Memorials from the Past", Qazvini's "Nujum" - "Stars", etc.), then artistic works. (Hariri's works such as "Maqamot", "Kalila and Dimna", "Tarihi Tabarii") were painted.

Fiction, mainly epic poetry - masnavi, epics (including Ferdavsi's "Shahnoma", "Hamsa" of Nizami, Khusrav Dekhdavi, Alisher Navoi, works of Jami, Sa'di, Hafiz Shirozi, etc.) are a separate category. In the East, after Moni, the names of Juna-id Baghdadi, Khoja Abdulhai, Mahmoud Siyokhaham, Ghiyosiddin Naqqosh, Mirak Naqqosh, Kamoliddin Behzod, Qasim Ali, Mahmud Muzahib, Abdulla Musavvir, Basavan, Rezayi Abbasi and others are famous in the East. It became a tradition to work on miniatures and create portraits of individuals, especially in India during the Babur period. At the beginning of the 8th century, a school of miniatures was formed in Bukhara. The miniature works of the Bukhara school of miniatures, made in the 8th-10th centuries, are now preserved in world museums, including the Louvre Museum of France and the Hermitage Museum of the American metropolitan Russia. Later, at the end of the 14th century, the Samarkand school of miniatures was formed in Samarkand, which later became Herat miniatures. influenced the formation of his school. The gardens in the gardens built by Amir Temur are also decorated with wall paintings. Separate libraries were established in the palaces of the Timurids, where skilled calligraphers and writers, including artists, worked there. During the period of Husayn Boygaro and Alisher Navoi, great attention was paid to the development of book art and miniatures. Miniature works of the Timurid, Shaibani, and Baburi eras are kept in the world's most prestigious museums, libraries, and private collections.

Portrait miniature as a special type of painting art was formed during the Renaissance, in terms of method and style, it is inextricably linked with book miniature, as well as with the general development of realistic art. In Germany, England, miniature works are distinguished by the accuracy and enrichment of the portrait and mental state (H. Holbein the Younger and his students). In the 16th century, enamel miniatures were developed in France. From the 18th century, it spread widely to Russia, the Italian R. Carriera introduced the method of painting with gouache on a colored ground on ivory, and the watercolor miniature rose to a high peak. In Europe, by the 17th and 18th centuries, miniatures were replaced by engraving, and lithography developed. From the 19th century, due to the spread of photography, the creation of portrait miniatures declined.

Istisna in Islam are fine and elegant miniatures created to decorate objects and books. Artistic miniature is a special type of fine art. Initially, this type of design was carried out by the order of the upper class and was considered an integral part of handwritten books, valuable manuscripts and chronicles. To create them, great skill and professionalism were required from the artist, the finer and brighter the drawing, the higher the value of the miniature, and it was considered an indicator of the author's high professional skill. In addition, miniatures were considered part of the decoration. Small, colorful paintings were used to decorate luxury items in the houses of rich merchants and in the palaces of khans. Historical chronicles, hunting and battle scenes, meeting and food details could be depicted in the miniatures. The process of creating a miniature is a very complicated and time-consuming process, which requires perseverance, great patience, a steady hand and a sharp eye, as well as the unlimited imagination of the author.

By the beginning of the 20th century, the development of miniature art stopped in the territory of Uzbekistan. Usta Momin, A. Siddiqi, G. Nikitin, Ch. The traditions of M. are observed in the work of artists such as Ahmarov and T. Muhamedov. In the 70s and 80s, there were attempts to restore miniature traditions. The real development of the miniature took place after the independence of Uzbekistan. Ch. Ahmarov continued the traditions of miniature art in his work, enriching it with new content and ideas. His students continued the work of their teacher and raised the miniature to a new level.

Miniature lacquer miniature has become a wide-ranging artistic style, covering miniatures on paper, cloth, leather, leather, and wall works. Currently, the development of miniatures is in 3 directions - namely manuscript (book) illustrations (T. Muhamedov, Sh. Muhamadjonov, M. Salimov, etc.), lokli M. (N. Kholmatov, A. Yoldoshev, Sh. Shoahmedov, etc.) and M. Creative research is being conducted on creating murals in the style of T. Boltaboyev, H. Nazirov, G. Kamolov - the first laureates of the State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Kamoliddin Behzod and others.

The skillful execution and completion of any work, thing, item, etc., by people means that the work of a person has been done artistically. Therefore, the pedagogue's careful, beautiful, impeccable execution of his work is considered an example of artistry.

The nature of the concept of fine art in education is a special scientific pedagogical analysis. That is why we should dwell on the existing theoretical concepts in this regard and their place in the science of pedagogy.

Fine art is an art in which the creator (sculptors and artists) depicts reality and existence through the use of shapes, lines, colors, paints in a certain space and etc. No matter how far the history of our ancestors is from us and no matter how unique their religious beliefs are, there are thin bridges that connect them with us. After all, it is the wonderful examples of art created by them, their spiritual values, their concepts and knowledge that have influenced the organic development of human thinking in general worldviews. Therefore, in the comprehensive training and formation of modern artist-teachers, we can refer to such examples of the heritage of the past, we can use them not only as examples of the past, but also as methodologically perfect tools in the educational process.

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